

DESIGN AND MATERIAL IMPLICATIONS OF COMPOSITE DRIVESHAFTS

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The general design requirements for automotive and truck driveshafts are described. Vibration, stiffness, torsion, and environmental effects are discussed, and a typical screening test for a carbon-glass hybrid shaft is given. The physical and mechanical properties of three low cost, fast cure epoxy based filament winding resin systems are described. The concept of a filament wound "layer" versus a prepreg layer is discussed relative to the laminate theory of design/analysis and a comparison of various hybrid driveshaft layering schemes is given, including the use of pure axial versus near axial plies. Finally, the sensitivity of various carbon fiber modulus levels on shaft performance is addressed.

INTRODUCTION

Since 1975 a number of independent development efforts have been undertaken in the United States, Europe, and Japan to determine the feasibility of carbon fiber composite automotive drivesh shafts. A variety of concepts have been proposed, prototyped, and tested, with varying degrees of success. Most of these concepts have used carbon/epoxy, either totally or in concert with glass. More recently, the hybrid approach has been pursued entirely because of its economic attractiveness. Reasons for using carbon fiber in this application have been well documented in References 1-4.

In general, the rotational speeds of the drive train require the torque tube to have a high natural frequency, and carbon fiber composites are uniquely suited for this application because of their high specific stiffness and due to the fact that the fiber direction and quantity (percent of total tube weight) may be adjusted to tune the shaft to meet specific drive train requirements. This is particularly attractive for light truck applications, where a one piece composite design can replace a two piece steel assembly with a weight savings of approximately 6.8 kilograms (15 pounds).

The geometric and performance characteristics (torque/vibration) of torque shafts can be broken down into four general automotive classes, namely compacts, sedans, light and heavy trucks. Typical requirements for each class are shown in Table 1. All these have been designed and prototyped in composites. Carbon fiber is needed only when the critical balance between torque, diameter, length, and frequency cannot be attained with metal or fiberglass. Naturally, some driveline systems need no carbon and while the light truck application appears to be the most logical at this time, others still represent viable markets.

The ultimate test of an automotive torqueshaft is a fleet trial. Before that, however, a series of screening tests are necessary to eliminate poor designs and marginal performers. A typical screening test for a light truck driveshaft is shown in Table 2. The ball impact is an arbitrary, yet realistic, condition to simulate foreign object damage. Fatigue and ultimate testing at both 121°C (250°F) and -40°C (-40°F) indicate the severe requirement on the resin system. Finally, the saturated salt water boil, though again realistic, is probably less severe than a simple water boil.

In the following sections, material and design implications are directed toward a specific class of composite shafts, namely those having carbon and glass fiber at the general orientations of 0, 45, and 90 degrees to the shaft axis. Also, only epoxy resin is considered.

Historically, early work concentrated on all carbon shafts with angles at ± 45 , 0 and 90 degrees. Variations included both the changing of angles for ease of fabrication (going from 0 to ± 10 degrees and from 90 to 80 degrees) and layer sequencing (for instance interchanging the radial placement of the ± 45 and 0 degree plies or splitting layers to achieve symmetry). Hybridization with glass evolved by 1978. Early attempts simply replaced the ± 45 degree carbon with glass, reasoning that glass could take the torque as well as carbon, and at 45 degrees, carbon contributed virtually nothing to axial stiffness. Logic also dictated that the hoop fibers be glass although this was not straight-forward since torsional buckling is one failure mode and hoop stiffness is a major concern.

The most recent optimization in layer technology is outlined in a patent by Yates and Rezin⁽⁵⁾ where a (± 45 glass/ ± 10 carbon/90 glass) sequence is changed to include a ± 10 glass layer, to minimize the ± 10 carbon. It was discovered that in some cases the critical failure mode of the shafts was torsional buckling rather than shear, and that the buckling resistance could be improved simply by adding wall thickness (regardless of angle). By adding 45 glass, effective axial modulus and thus bending frequency decreased and more axial carbon was required. But

by adding glass at low angles the frequency was unaffected. Many filament wound shafts have been so constructed and successfully tested.

FILAMENT WINDING

A number of fabrication schemes have been tried over the years. Based upon a previous study (6), filament winding appears to be the most promising for production economics. Conventional filament winding has been used on many of the prototype shafts to date. Here, a single band of fiber (either carbon or glass) is wet with resin and wound back and forth onto a rotating mandrel until the entire pattern (an integral plus-minus layer) is completed. Typical winding times for a single shaft consisting of multiple plies and angles is 30 to 60 minutes. Another concept, typically used to make large pipes, winds on a complete plus (or minus) layer in one pass by feeding hundreds of yarns simultaneously onto a rotating and translating mandrel. This method, which is being adapted for drive-shafts (6,7), will wind one shaft per minute, which is considered to be within automotive production rate requirements.

MATERIAL IMPLICATIONS - RESIN

The operating temperature range for most driveshafts is between -40°C and 121°C (-40°F to 250°F). They must operate in a hot wet environment, and be resistant to stone impingement and other foreign object damage. Also, resistance to salt solutions is needed since salt is used to control road ice formation. All the above place more demands on the resin than the fibers. The resin is further constrained since it must be filament windable, possess a fast cure, and be relatively inexpensive. The strategy used here has been to develop the best possible resin system, subject to the last three constraints, mechanically characterize the resin and the resin-fiber systems, then develop design allowables based upon those properties. Three such epoxy systems are described in Tables 3, 4, and 5. System B is suitable for 149°C (300°F) operation, while A and C are usable only to 121°C (250°F). Note that the characterization includes unidirectional tensile, flexure, and short beam shear, and is reasonably complete by most standards. However, a driveshaft typically contains ± 45 degree fiber which takes all torsion loads. ± 45 degree rail shear or torsion tube tests are needed to generate material design values, but those tests are expensive to run. Our practice has been to use the generally accepted values of ± 45 degree shear strength $\sim 206\text{--}275\text{MPa}$ ($30\text{--}40\text{ksi}$) - for glass and reduce those values at 121°C (250°F) by the same ratio as the $23^{\circ}\text{C}/121^{\circ}\text{C}$ ($73^{\circ}\text{F}/250^{\circ}\text{F}$) flexure strengths. These then become the new design strengths for 121°C (250°F) performance. Further reductions account for fatigue strength at temperature. This approach appears to be satisfactory, since we have had no tube failures at design load at 121°C (250°F). The implication here is that the design process can overcome resin shear deficiencies so long as reasonable resin properties can be maintained at elevated temperatures.

MATERIAL IMPLICATIONS - FIBER

High Strength Versus High Modulus Fiber

The use of high strength versus high modulus carbon fiber as the stiffening element in composite driveshafts has been debated for some time. Both types of shafts have been made and successfully tested, although high strength models predominate simply because of that fibers' availability, superior handling characteristics, higher shear strength, and lower cost. The design implication of using high modulus fiber is that for a specific shaft requirement: (1) less high modulus than high strength fiber will be needed to develop the necessary stiffness, (2) lower shear strength allowables in the high modulus fiber will require more glass to absorb the torque, and (3) can the cost differential of using high modulus fiber be offset by using less of it.

A study compared the two fibers in the driveshaft application, varying fiber volume content, tubular geometry, and design requirements. These are shown in Table 6, with the results tabulated in Table 7.

In the study, all shafts used an inner 45 degree and outer 90 degree glass layer. Longitudinal carbon fiber at 0 degree was placed between the glass layers. Each design had the carbon fiber thickness adjusted to give a critical speed as close as possible to the requirement. Also, the 45 degree glass plies were the same thickness for all shafts of a given configuration. It was assumed that all torsion was taken by the 45 degree plies and their thickness was chosen based on an allowable shear stress level which was the same for all designs. In all cases, the 90 degree glass was .25mm (.010 inch) thick. Finally, the torsion buckling safety factor was 1.5 and additional glass at 0 degree was added between the carbon and 45 degree glass when necessary to build up buckling thickness.

As one would anticipate, the efficiency of each driveshaft configuration improved as the modulus of the carbon fiber used in the 0° ply increased. Hence the most carbon fiber is required using high strength fiber at low fiber volume, while the least fiber is required for high modulus fiber at high fiber volume. As shown in Table 7, if the carbon 0° ply is wound at 55% fiber volume, approximately 40%-50% less carbon fiber is required using high modulus fiber than high strength fiber. At 70% fiber volume the range of savings is approximately 30%-40% depending on the configuration under discussion. On the average, reductions of 35%-45% of carbon fiber weight are possible in a driveshaft design similar to those presented here through substitution of high modulus fiber for high strength fiber. This conclusion assumes, however, that the design is not constrained by the shear stress in the longitudinal carbon plies. If that shear stress is limited to 34.5MPa (5000psi) for high strength fiber and 27.6MPa (4000psi) for high modulus fiber, then the previous weight reductions are closer to 20-25%. The ideal fiber would be one with high modulus and high shear strength at the sacrifice of tensile strength.

DESIGN IMPLICATIONS

This section addresses three specific issues. These include (1) design and performance differences due to discrete versus interwoven layers of angle plies, (2) stress and stiffness differences between 0 degree longitudinal and ±10 degree near longitudinal placement of fibers, and (3) the effects of non-symmetry in the tubular laminate.

Discrete Plies

The conventional filament winding process will lay down a double "ply" of plus and minus layers. Depending upon winding parameters, the diamond pattern of bands may be large or small, but typically each diamond is about 10-20 square centimeters. Different layers with different bandwidths and angles make the shaft difficult to analyze from a pure laminate standpoint. It is simpler to assume that the shaft has the same radial sequence of plies throughout. In fact, this is the case for a shaft wound with the full layer delivery system previously discussed. A series of shafts were wound by Celanese and Rockwell Automotive Division using the discrete and interwoven concepts. All had an inner layer of 45 degree glass, a second layer of ±10 degree glass, a third layer of ±10 degree carbon, and finally a 90 degree hoop wrap of glass. The amounts of carbon and glass in all shafts was identical. Though the absolute test results remain proprietary, the following general conclusions were reached:

1. Little, if any, difference in frequency response could be attributed to the discrete versus interwoven layers.
2. Higher fiber volumes could be attained with the discrete scheme because of better packing.
3. No discernable differences were noted in tube torsional strengths.

Axial Plies

The use of 10 degree versus 0 degree plies for axial stiffness is both a fabrication preference and a design requirement. The implications of both are important. Table 8 demonstrates the effect on stiffness and strength for two designs. In the first set, ± 10 degree glass and ± 10 degree carbon layers are replaced with 0 degree layers of equivalent thickness. Note that the 5 percent increase in critical frequency is offset by the 30-40 percent increase in shear stress in both the 45 degree glass and 0 degree carbon. The implication is that true axial plies improve tube stiffness, but do not support the torsional load. If failure is defined as σ_{12} ultimate shear in the longitudinal carbon or glass plies, or as σ_{xy} shear (most probable) in the ± 45 degree glass plies, then the ± 10 degree tubes are considerably stronger. The same differences are noted in the 45/0/90 and 45/10/90 configurations. For these reasons, the authors favored a slight (approximately 10 degree) angle in the longitudinal plies.

Symmetry

The composite driveshaft described here is a laminated, hybrid glass carbon structure. Unless a laminated composite is layered in a symmetric fashion, there will be shear-stretching and bending-stretching between the membrane and bending responses. From a filament winding standpoint, it is not realistic to mass produce driveshafts using a symmetric sequence. The examples given so far, containing each angle in a "lumped" fashion, are easier to prototype as well as manufacture.

Classical laminated plate theory provides a convenient basis for composite driveshaft design/analysis. This theory is based on the Kirchhoff hypothesis for thin, flat laminates of generally orthotropic layers and it provides for the evaluation of the coupled responses between shearing/stretching and bending/stretching in flat laminates. A driveshaft tube, however, is a curved laminate with an axisymmetric geometry. The most complete treatment of this phenomena was given by Brown and Rezin⁽⁸⁾ in 1979. They used two approaches for investigating the use of classical plate theory for predicting overall performance of axisymmetric driveshaft tubes. The first approach was the simple membrane method commonly used for thin-walled tubes of homogeneous, isotropic materials. The second approach was to modify the classical stiffness formulation by including the strain distribution required by the geometric symmetry and the mechanics assumption that plane sections remain plane. These were referred to as the membrane method (coupled and uncoupled) and the enforced symmetry method.

As an example of the first, Table 9 shows the effect of layering sequence on symmetry (B_{11}/A_{11}) with and without the membrane coupling included. Note that without coupling, the membrane solution predicts the same stiffness and frequency regardless of attempts to make the layers "more symmetric" by splitting the ± 45 ply or interlocating the ± 10 and ± 45 degree glass plies. With coupling, frequency approaches the uncoupled values for the "more symmetric" sequences. In actual testing of 14 filament wound driveshafts, Brown and Rezin concluded that there was good test correlation with the enforced symmetry and uncoupled membrane analyses. The coupled membrane analysis results were particularly poor for highly unsymmetric laminates with B_{11}/A_{11} on the order of -0.02 . They attributed this to the lack of agreement between the actual strain distribution and the distribution considered by the method. Both the enforced symmetry method and the uncoupled membrane analysis method results showed good agreement over the range of B_{11}/A_{11} ratios tested.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the developmental work described in this study, it is believed that the following conclusions are valid:

1. Adequate design and analysis methods exist to accurately and reliably predict composite driveshaft performance in terms of natural frequency and torsional buckling, together with acceptable fatigue and ultimate strength performance.
2. Resin systems have been developed which meet automotive requirements with respect to fast cure, mechanical properties, and environmental resistance.
3. Prototype composite shafts have demonstrated the predicted weight savings and performance gains over existing steel shafts.
4. Economic studies indicate that the composite driveshaft, in selected applications, is cost competitive with steel shafts.

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<u>TYPICAL REQUIREMENTS</u>	<u>UNITS</u>	<u>COMPACTS</u>	<u>SEDANS</u>	<u>LIGHT TRUCKS</u>	<u>HEAVY TRUCKS</u>
Length between yoke centers	cm (in)	114 (45)	140 (55)	190 (75)	254 (100)
Inside Diameter	cm (in)	6.98(2.75)	6.98(2.75)	9.53(3.75)	11.4(4.5)
Maximum Static Torque	Nm (ft.lb.)	1693(1250)	2818(2080)	3387(2500)	10840(8000)

TABLE 1

DRIVESHAFT PERFORMANCE REQUIREMENTS

-
-
1. Measure EI by 3 Point Bending
 2. Static Torque to 3048 Nm(2250ft.lb.)
 3. 24 Hr. Saturated salt water boil
 4. At -40°C (-40°F), drop 0.9kg (2 lb.) steel ball from 1.82m (6 ft.) height onto center of V-block supported tube
 5. At 121°C (250°F) static torque to 3048Nm(2250ft.lb.)
 6. At 121°C (250°F), fatigue for 120,000 reversed cycles at 1504Nm(1110ft.lb.)
 7. Recheck critical speed, measure EI
 8. Static Torque to failure (>3048Nm, 2250ft.lb.)
 9. Also perform static and fatigue torque tests at -40°C (-40°F) and ambient (other shafts)

TABLE 2

TYPICAL SCREENING TEST SEQUENCE FOR A LIGHT TRUCK DRIVESHAFT

(Maximum Design Torque = 3048Nm, 2250ft.lb.)

Property	Units	Sys. A	Sys. C
Viscosity	CPS	2040 at 55°C	950 at 65°C
Tecam Gel Time	Min.	145 at 55°C	337 at 65°C
Tg (dry casting)	°C (°F)	160 (320)	156 (313)
Tg (7 day water boil)	°C (°F)	132 (270)	154 (309)
Rockwell Hardness (M)		106	106
Heat Deflection Temp.	(°F)	161 (322)	148 (298)
Flex. Strength, 23°C	MPa (ksi)	110 (15.9)	139 (20.2)
121°C	MPa (ksi)	69.6 (10.1)	79.3 (11.5)
Flex Modulus, 23°C	GPa (Msi)	3.15 (.45)	3.17 (.46)
121°C	GPa (Msi)	2.0 (.29)	2.48 (.36)
Tensile Strength, 23°C	MPa (ksi)	76.5 (11.1)	73.8 (10.7)
Tensile Modulus, 23°C	GPa (Msi)	3.24 (.47)	3.38 (.49)
Elongation, 23°C	%	3.0	4.2

TABLE 3

TYPICAL RESIN AND CASTING PROPERTIES FOR EPOXY
 BASED FILAMENT WINDING SYSTEMS

Property	Test Temp, °C	Sys. A	Sys. B	Sys. C
Flex Strength dry	23	1503 (218)	1455 (211)	1510 (219)
	121	1013 (147)	1020 (148)	951 (138)
	149	765 (111)	807 (117)	772 (112)
Flex Modulus dry	23	45 (6.6)	44 (6.4)	45 (6.5)
	121	43 (6.3)	43 (6.2)	38 (5.5)
	149	39 (5.7)	39 (5.7)	39 (5.7)
SBS Strength dry	23	83 (12.0)	94 (13.6)	87 (12.6)
	121	51 (7.4)	57 (8.3)	55 (8.0)
	149	28 (4.0)	50 (7.2)	46 (6.7)
Flex Strength wet	23	1330 (193)	1248 (181)	1365 (198)
	121	800 (116)	924 (134)	813 (118)
	149	-	696 (101)	-
Flex Modulus wet	23	48 (6.9)	43 (6.3)	44 (6.4)
	121	41 (6.0)	45 (6.5)	41 (5.9)
	149	-	39 (5.6)	-
SBS Strength wet	23	77 (11.2)	91 (13.2)	81 (11.7)
	121	46 (6.6)	50 (7.3)	42 (6.1)
	149	-	40 (5.8)	-

Strength in MPa (ksi)
 Modulus in GPa (Msi)
 Flex values normalized to 62% Fiber Volume
 Wet conditioned 24 hours boiling water, tested wet
 Cure: 5 min. at 177°C (9.5 min. for Sys. B)

TABLE 4

UNIDIRECTIONAL PROPERTIES OF FILAMENT WOUND E GLASS EPOXY

Property	Test Temp, °C	Sys. A.		Sys. B		Sys. C	
Flex Strength, dry	23	1717	(249)	1758	(255)	1524	(221)
	121	1151	(167)	1213	(176)	1089	(158)
	149	979	(142)	1089	(158)	889	(129)
Flex Modulus dry	23	125	(18.1)	133	(19.3)	128	(18.6)
	121	121	(17.5)	130	(18.8)	127	(18.5)
	149	119	(17.2)	127	(18.4)	120	(17.4)
SBS Strength dry	23	92	(13.4)	100	(14.5)	83	(12.1)
	121	59	(8.6)	68	(9.8)	52	(7.6)
	149	50	(7.2)	55	(8.0)	46	(6.6)
Flex Strength wet	23	1468	(213)	1434	(208)	1510	(219)
	121	827	(120)	938	(136)	958	(139)
	149	-		855	(124)	-	
Flex Modulus wet	23	121	(17.6)	125	(18.2)	129	(18.7)
	121	115	(16.7)	123	(17.8)	125	(18.2)
	149	-		119	(17.2)	-	
SBS Strength wet	23	80	(11.6)	93	(13.5)	77	(11.1)
	121	34	(4.7)	57	(8.3)	46	(6.7)
	149	-		46	(6.6)	-	

Strength in MPa (ksi)

Modulus in GPa (Msi)

Flex values normalized to 62% Fiber Volume

Wet conditioned 24 hours boiling water, tested wet

Cure: 5 min. at 177°C (9.5 min. for Sys. B)

TABLE 5

UNIDIRECTIONAL PROPERTIES OF FILAMENT WOUND CELION 6000 EPOXY

REQUIREMENTS	SHAFT CONFIGURATION			
	1		2	
Yoke Center Distance, cm(in.)	140	(55)	191	(75)
Inner Diameter, cm(in.)	7.5	(2.75)	8.5	(3.35)
Torque, Nm(ft.lb.)	1355	(1000)	2033	(1500)
Critical Speed, hz	150		100	
CARBON FIBER	COMPOSITE PROPERTIES			
	55% Fiber Vol.		70% Fiber Vol.	
High Strength				
Modulus, GPa (Msi)	124	(18)	165	(24)
Density, g/cc (pcu)	1.52	(.055)	1.60	(.058)
High Modulus				
Modulus, GPa (Msi)	179	(26)	241	(35)
Density, g/cc (pcu)	1.57	(.057)	1.66	(.060)

TABLE 6

CONFIGURATION AND MATERIAL REQUIREMENTS

FOR HIGH STRENGTH/HIGH MODULUS STUDY

Configuration	Fiber	Fiber Volume	Carbon Fiber Wt. kg (lb.)	Wt. Saving* Percent
1	H. Stren.	55	.84 (1.86)	
1	H. Stren.	70	.65 (1.44)	
1	H. Mod.	55	.47 (1.03)	45
1	H. Mod.	70	.39 (.85)	41
2	H. Stren.	55	1.67 (3.68)	
2	H. Stren.	70	1.24 (2.74)	
2	H. Mod.	55	.88 (1.94)	47
2	H. Mod.	70	.77 (1.70)	38

* % Wt. savings = $\frac{\text{H. Stren. Fiber Wt.} - \text{H. Mod. Fiber Wt.}}{\text{H. Stren. Fiber Wt.}}$

TABLE 7

FIBER WEIGHT SAVINGS WITH HIGH MODULUS VERSUS HIGH STRENGTH FIBER

Layer Sequence (Inner → Outer)	E GPa (Msi)	EI 10^6kgm^2 (10^6lb.in.^2)	Crit. Freq. hertz	$\sigma_{xy}(\text{Max})$ in $\pm 45^\circ$ ply MPa (ksi)	$\sigma_{12}(\text{Max})$ in carbon ply MPa (ksi)
$\pm 45^\circ$ glass / 0° glass / 0° carb / 90° glass .10(.04)/.076(.03)/.13(.05)/.025(.01)	65.2 (9.46)	.338 (29.37)	104.9	106.8 (15.5)	42.2 (6.12)
$\pm 45^\circ$ glass / $\pm 10^\circ$ glass / $\pm 10^\circ$ carb / 90° glass .10(.04)/.076(.03)/.13(.05)/.025(.01)	60.5 (8.78)	.313 (27.23)	100.9	81.3 (11.8)	30.1 (4.37)
$\pm 45^\circ$ glass / 0° carb / 90° glass .10(.04)/.13(.05)/.025(.01)	73.4 (10.65)	.286 (24.82)	111.3	118.6 (17.2)	46.7 (6.78)
$\pm 45^\circ$ glass / $\pm 10^\circ$ carb / 90° glass .10(.04)/.13(.05)/.025(.01)	70.0 (9.86)	.265 (23.0)	107.1	91.7 (13.3)	34.0 (4.93)

Layer dimensions are cm(in)
 Tube length = 177cm (70 in)
 Inner diameter = 9.65cm (3.8 in)
 Torque = 2822Nm (2083ft.lb)
 Coupling symmetry [B] = 0

TABLE 8
 EFFECT OF LONGITUDINAL ANGLE ON TUBE STIFFNESS AND SHEAR STRESS

Layer Sequence (Inner → Outer)	Ex GPa (Msi)		EI $10^6 \text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^2$ ($10^6 \text{lb}\cdot\text{in}^2$)		Critical Frequency hertz		$\sigma_{xy}(\text{Max})$ in $\pm 45^\circ$ ply MPa(ksi)		B_{11}/A_{11}	
	B=0	B≠0	B=0	B≠0	B=0	B≠0	B=0	B≠0	B=0	B≠0
	$\pm 45^\circ$ glass / $\pm 10^\circ$ glass / $\pm 10^\circ$ carb / 90° glass .10(.04) / .076(.03) / .13(.05) / .025(.01)	60.5 (8.78)	31.1 (4.51)	.312 (27.2)	.161 (14.0)	100.9	72.4	81.3 (11.8)	87.6 (12.7)	0
$\pm 10^\circ$ glass / $\pm 45^\circ$ glass / $\pm 10^\circ$ carb / 90° glass .076(.03) / .10(0.04) / .13(.05) / .025(.01)	60.5 (8.78)	44.7 (6.49)	.312 (27.2)	.232 (20.2)	100.9	86.9	80.6 (11.7)	92.3 (13.4)	0	-.0166
$\pm 45^\circ$ glass / $\pm 10^\circ$ glass / $\pm 10^\circ$ carb / $\pm 45^\circ$ glass / 90° glass .05(.02) / .076(.03) / .13(.05) / .05(.02) / .025(.01)	60.5 (8.78)	56.6 (8.21)	.312 (27.2)	.293 (25.5)	100.9	97.6	80.6 (11.7)	93.8 (13.6)	0	-.004

Layer Dimensions are cm(in)
 Tube length = 177cm (70 in)
 Inner diameter = 9.65cm (3.8 in)
 Torque = 2822Nm (2083ft.lb)

B = [B] = Coupling matrix

B = 0 No coupling

TABLE 9
 EFFECT OF SYMMETRY ASSUMPTION ON TUBE STIFFNESS (MEMBRANE METHOD)